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Research Article

AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON THE OCCURRENCE OF ANXIETY IN EMPLOYED AND NON-EMPLOYED FEMALES IN ACCORDANCE WITH THEIR FAMILY RESTRICTION

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Abstract:

Objective: This study aimed to check the availability of the anxiety in employed and non-employed females in accordance with their qualification, system of family & amount of the children.

Study Setting: This research work conducted in Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

Study Design: This research work was a non-experimental research work.

Methodology: The total amount of 100 females with 50 employed females and 50 no employed females were the part of this research work. There was matching in the age, qualification, profession and social as well as economic status of the members. Administration of TMAS (Taylor manifest anxiety scale) carried out on all females to evaluate the presence of anxiety among them. Interview of all the females carried out to put the data of demography in records.

Results: We observed the anxiety in 57.0% females of study; 74.0% were the non-employed females & thirty six percent employed females found with anxiety. We found an important relationship between the anxiety and amount of children and their qualification. We found no significant relationship between anxiety and system of family.

Conclusion: The findings of this case work concluded that there should be a moral support for all non-employed females. They should be permit to recreate themselves by visiting the recreation points outside the home restrictions.

Keywords: Spontaneity, Anxiety, Employed, Qualification, Moral, Wearisomeness, Interview.

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INTRODUCTION:

It is a reality that the complaints of wearisomeness are very common from the lives of housewives. They usually think that they have no time to recreate themselves, all the day, they have to take care of the children and work for household activities. In comparison with the employed females, housewives has very limited social circle. Only single person to appreciate the hard work of the females in the houses is her husband. A female with five children and one husband and with no help or money support cannot get leisure and other recreation activities. The employed females are appreciate able persons of the society & they are independent and able to earn money. On other way, majority of employed females find that their children give the common interest focus for those females as well as their life partners and most of them think that the time spent to children came with outcome in lack of sharing and lack of spontaneity in the husband-wife relationship [1, 2].

There are multi-dimensional issues faced by employed females and there categorization carried out in three kinds as social, metal and environmental problems. The participation in the other activities outside house includes extra burden for these females who are also responsible for many home responsibilities. More mental problems can be present among employed females. But various research woks conducted in different areas of the world showed that it is not correct. Employment has a positive impact on females of lower social and economic class. In comparison of both groups of females, Mukhopadhyay displayed a strong association score of anxiety and scores of health [3].

Many recent works have the view that persons can get more profit while performing multiple task and roles. Current research works of dangers and profits of performing multiple roles show that people with more social role faced less metal distress or illness [4, 5]. The main important factors which lead the non-employed females to metal depression are low income of the family, clashes among husband and wife, abuses language by family of husband and high amount of children [6].

METHODOLOGY:

There were two groups in this research work in which one group was of employed women (EW) and second group was of non-employed women (NEW). The comparison of the scores of anxiety carried among females of both groups. Purposive sampling method was in use for the selection of the participants. The EW were from different profession having same working hours and same social and economic status. NEW group participants selected after the interview of one of our member with same social and economic status and level of qualification. There were 50 EW and fifty NEW in the research work. We also considered the qualification and age of the participants.

After their selection, investigator contacted the all participants. Investigator gave them the surety of their confidentiality. The interview of those females did not carry out who found hesitant to take part in this work. The study standard took the less than 10 year education as lo education level and more than 10 years of education as high education level. We considered high amount of children when females found with more than 3 children. Further study of the females who were suffering from the anxiety carried accordance with their level of qualification, system of family and amount of their children. The average age of the female participants was 38.52 ± 0.81 years.

The anxiety scale of Taylor manifest was in use for the evaluation of the anxiety among the females of NEW and EW groups. This is a self-report containing about fifty questions to evaluate the anxiety prevalence among patients [7]. SPSS V.10 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. Students' T test was in use for the measurement of the association about anxiety between two groups. The method of Chi square test was in use to check the relationship between different categorical variables.

RESULTS:

We discovered the anxiety in 57.0% females of this research work. We observed that majority of non-employed females were suffering from anxiety (74.0%) in comparisons with the presence of anxiety in employed females (36.0%). We found significant association in this occurrence (Table-1).

Table-I: Presence of anxiety in working and non-working women

Category	Anxiety Prevalence				Total	
	Negative		Affirmative		No	Percentage
	No	Percentage	No	Percentage		
Working Women	32.0	64.00	18.0	36.00	50.0	50.00

Non-working women	11.0	22.00	39.0	74.00	50.0	50.00
TOTAL	43.0	43.00	57.0	57.00	100.0	100.00

We also found an important association among two groups when we compared the females of both groups for their qualification level. The result of this work

shows that most of unemployed females (84.60%) suffering from anxiety were available with < 10 year of qualification (Table-2).

Table II: Education of women presented with anxiety

Category	Education				Total	
	Low		High		No	Percentage
	No	Percentage	No	Percentage		
Working Women	9.0	50.00	9.0	50.00	18.0	31.60
Non-working women	33.0	84.60	6.0	15.40	39.0	68.40
TOTAL	42.0	73.70	15.0	26.30	57.0	100.00

Current research work showed that females from both group living in the system of joint family were more

prone to anxiety but this association was not much significant (Table-3).

Table III: Family system of women presented with anxiety

Category	Family System				Total	
	Joint		Nucleus		No	Percentage
	No	Percentage	No	Percentage		
Working Women	13.0	72.20	5.0	27.80	18.0	31.60
Non-working women	24.0	61.50	15.0	38.50	39.0	68.40
TOTAL	37.0	64.90	20.0	35.10	57.0	100.00

We found a significant relationship between the quantity of children and score of anxiety. This case

work displayed that most of the unemployed females (79.50%) suffering from anxiety were available with

more than 3 children as compared to the employed females (11.10%) (Table-4).

Table IV: Number of children of women presented with anxiety

Category	Number of Children				Total	
	Low		High			
	No	Percentage	No	Percentage	No	Percentage
Working Women	16.0	88.90	2.0	11.10	18.0	31.60
Non-working women	8.0	20.50	31.0	79.50	39.0	68.40
TOTAL	24.0	42.10	33.0	57.90	57.0	100.00

DISCUSSION:

The results of this research work about the high occurrence of the anxiety among females without employment are similar to the outcomes of Mukhpadhyay, Cilli & Rani and Yadav [3, 8, 2]. These studies showed that females without employment showed high average score of anxiety in comparison with the employed females. They concluded that scores of anxiety were increasing with the increase of the age and amount of children. Some of the important reasons for the high rate of anxiety among housewives are social or economic condition, less education level and their participation in less roles of society. There are a lot of responsibilities for the females of our society. Females in our society face conflicts of house, have less, low amount of rights, and no social or economic liberty. The females of society face much problems from tradition and old values of cultures.

The work performed by the females is obligatory work without any payment. Deficiency of the advantages and positive qualification are the causative factors for the reduction in the well-being of mind and rise in the despair, anxiety & stress. All types of depression may

be the reason of less control at home, which normally leads to high rate of anxiety in housewives. Griffin JM also stated the high prevalence of depression & anxiety in the females with less control at home [9]. The participation of the housewives in less roles of society is also the causative factor in the development of anxiety because they like to rely on their role of housewives for the identity of themselves. Having multiple roles increase the knowledge of females and provide them a chance to learn more to establish their self-esteem. Performing multiple roles also give cognitive cushioning & substitute sources of gratification when the incidence come diversely in single domain of life [10]. Less education is one of the causes for the development of the anxiety. It is the fact that deficiency of the formal education is the main risk factor for the development of mental complications. High Qualification level increases self-efficacy and makes the females to feel without sensitivity in various conditions and give them a better sense to control or handle the surroundings [11].

CONCLUSION:

The results of this research work concluded that anxiety is more prevalent in the females without employment in comparison with the females with employment. The important causative factors may be the less level of qualification, their participation in less social roles and their social condition in the society. There is suggestion that there should be encouragement for females to increase their level of education and they should perform more social roles to decrease of the risks causing the development of anxiety.

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